

Using Social Media in Engineering Support and Space Flight Operations Control

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Abstract—Word processing was one of the earliest uses for small workstations, but we quickly learned that desktop computers were far more than e-typewriters. Similarly, social media offers tools that could significantly improve our effectiveness at managing the avalanche of information and decisions associated with space flight projects. However, “could” does not necessarily equal “should”. We must wield two-edged swords carefully to avoid stabbing ourselves.

NASA’s Marshall Space Flight Center (MSFC) provides 1) Engineering Support for multiple space flight projects, 2) NASA payloads planning, integration, and execution, and international payload inputs integration for the International Space Station (ISS), 3) operations capability for onsite and remote payload users, and 4) Backup Control Center (BCC) capability for JSC’s ISS Mission Control Center (MCC-H).

This paper examines how social media might enhance and in some cases simplify such efforts, discusses cultural implications and issues, and summarizes MSFC’s current efforts to apply social media to institutional, engineering, and operations architectures and applications.^{1 2}

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INTRODUCTION

Developmental engineering support for NASA flight projects provides underpinning across design, development, and test phases, and deals with vast quantities of data across a broad range of times and events, frequently requiring comparison and analysis of multiple instances of events, e.g., rocket engine firings, stress tests, etc. Flight control also requires monitoring and evaluation of a phenomenal amount of data. Some situations, e.g., launch, dynamic flight, and critical or emergency launch vehicle and/or Space Station operations, require split-second, crystal clear decisions. Other scenarios, such as payload operations and/or station keeping, require contemplation of multiple options over an extended period of time, accounting for both specific instances and accumulated trends.

What could social media possibly have to do with this?

At first glance, social media and the technical disciplines we’re discussing would appear to be light years apart, the former being loose and flexible, and the latter tightly controlled and disciplined.

One problem is that well-known examples of social media, e.g., Facebook® and Twitter®, are usually experienced (or often merely observed as activities of our friends and/or families) in the sense of “social” as “recreational relationships”, and much of what happens in that context appears frivolous. However, “social” also refers to “interactions among organisms and their collective co-existence.” This is just as important as interactions among aeronautical systems and their collective co-existence.

While NASA uses Web 2.0 collaborative tools to a good extent for public affairs, the tools are new to MSFC as a whole, as well as to local Engineering Support activities, technically and especially culturally. A social media environment for MSFC centerwide use is expected to “go live” in early 2011, and some major Engineering Support environments that include social media capability are discussed later in this paper.

Discussions with about 50 colleagues indicate that fewer than 20% can readily define the core mechanisms, strengths, and contexts of the tools in a work environment, though most have had contact with some tools, often at home.

¹ U.S. Government work not protected by U.S. copyright
² IEEEAC paper#1119, Version 1, Updated January 7, 2011

Just what is “Web 2.0”? The term was popularized by Tim O’Reilly, founder of a major U.S. technology transfer firm and a promoter of the open software movement. In 2004, he and other computer industry gurus observed that companies that survived the bursting of the dot-com bubble³ had certain things in common that were fundamentally different than before the collapse. [1]

In O’Reilly’s words, “...Web 2.0 doesn't have a hard boundary, but rather, a gravitational core. You can visualize Web 2.0 as a set of principles and practices that tie together a veritable solar system of sites that demonstrate some or all of those principles, at a varying distance from that core.” Figure 1 illustrates this concept and Figure 2 summarizes it.

Figure 1 – Web 2.0: A Gravitational Core and its Resulting Solar System [2]

<p>Web 2.0 Key Points:</p> <p>Emphasize services over content. Users manage the data and how it reaches them Promote online collaboration and sharing among users.</p>	<p>Web 1.0 vs. Web 2.0:</p> <p>Web 1.0 was commerce. Web 2.0 is people. Web 1.0 and email are one-to-many. Web 2.0 is many-to-many, with one-to-one capabilities.</p>
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Figure 2 – Web 2.0 in Fifty Words

Note – Much of Web 2.0 has a “free to the end user” appearance that relies significantly on Web advertising to pay service providers. Of course, government and restricted user base sites typically don’t have advertising, so such entities may contract with the provider for dedicated/secure servers or license the technology and host it themselves.

SIGNIFICANT TERMS

Table 1 identifies some major techniques and applications typical of Web 2.0. Subsequent discussion focuses on how these can benefit engineering support and/or flight operations. Many improvements pertain to endeavors in other disciplines as well. (Some terms are included for awareness, but are not discussed.)

³ The dot-com bubble was a 1995-2001 stock market boom and bust cycle fueled by speculation in tech industry firms, especially internet companies. More at: <http://www.wisegeek.com/what-was-the-dot-com-bubble.htm>

Term	Explanation	Comments
Social Media	Media designed to be disseminated through social interaction, created using highly accessible and scalable publishing techniques.	Transform broadcast media monologues (one to many) into collaborative dialogues (many to many).
Blog	A diary published on the Internet or an intranet, usually written by an individual but sometimes by corporate bodies. A blog's home page usually shows the most recent article and links to earlier articles, the owner's profile, and web logs written by the owner's friends. There is usually a facility for readers to add comments to the bottom of articles.	<p>The ease of creating comments and discussion threads contributes to the easy exchange of ideas. Information is free-flowing and discoverable, as opposed to 'stovepiped' and sanitized.</p> <p>Reader comments to blog entries provide valuable perspective and contrasts, plus answers to questions, problems, issues, or opportunities raised in or triggered by the main post. These may be of value to both the blogger and other readers.</p> <p>Content appears only once, as opposed to email chains with the same text copied multiple times. There are no headers or distribution lists to obscure the real discussion. See Figure 3.</p>
Wiki	A collaborative website that users can easily modify via a web browser. A typical wiki allows participants to edit, delete or modify content, including the work of other authors. This has worked surprisingly well because contributors tend to be more numerous and persistent than vandals, and old versions of pages are archived automatically. (It is possible to limit editing but allow comments.) Wikis are often used to power community websites, for personal note taking, in corporate intranets, and in knowledge management systems. "Wiki" (pronounced "wick-ee" or "vick-ee") is a Hawaiian word for "fast."	In a manner similar to blogs, wikis eliminate the proliferation of email chains with embedded content. Interested parties spend their time editing, not transmitting/receiving. See Figure 4.
RSS	A de facto, XML-based standard for automatic syndication of Web content, typically blogs, news, etc., but other web applications may also be syndicated. Site authors create an RSS feed of their content and register it with an RSS publisher. Users configure their reader to subscribe to desired feeds. RSS readers show changes for all feeds that a user opts into, but original feed can be accessed for in-depth research. The most common breakout of the acronym is "Really Simple Syndication." Other breakouts refer to the same method.	<p>Instead of spending time searching sites of interest to find information, new information on those sites finds the user. By using a reader application or web site instead of email, the information is available and consolidated and not an interruption.</p> <p>In workplace settings, conducting a project with a web tool with an RSS feed provides more incremental, timely updates to the team and the project manager than periodic emails and status meetings. This hones troubleshooting and enhancement activities.</p>
Social Network Site or Service (SNS)	A website and/or application that builds online communities of people who share interests and/or activities, or who are interested in exploring the interests and activities of others. SNSs encourage new ways to communicate and share information. Examples: Facebook®, MySpace, LinkedIn, Twitter®, Yammer.	Facilitates sharing of information through the social graph, the digital mapping of people's real-world social connections. Connections and development of the community can be as important as the information.

Term	Explanation	Comments
Tag	A non-hierarchical keyword or term assigned to a piece of information (such as a web page, blog post, digital image, or data file computer). This kind of metadata helps describe an item and allows it to be found again by browsing or searching.	Tags are chosen informally and personally by the item's creator and/or viewer. Tagging is an important feature of many Web 2.0 services, and is also part of some desktop software.
Folksonomy	Collaborative creation and management of tags to annotate and categorize content.	Bottom-up classification system means information conforms to users' preferences instead of forcing users to conform their thinking to the data's presentation. In most cases, any user can add a tag. The ability to search on tags makes information more discoverable to other users.
Facebook®	An extremely popular SNS with over 500 million active users. About 250 million log on in any given day. Users create and customize their own profiles with photos, videos, and information about themselves. Friends can browse the profiles of other friends and write public or private messages on their pages.	(See SNS definition)
Microblogging	The use of very limited-length postings and "following" techniques such that users tend to gather around common interests. See more under Twitter® and Yammer®.	
Twitter®	A free social networking and micro-blogging service. Users send and read "tweets", text-based posts up to 140 characters long. Users may subscribe to – "follow" – others' tweets, and may view them via browser, dedicated app, and/or receive via email or mobile phone text message. Also permits direct messages between individual users.	Archives of an individual's tweets are readily available, even if not following them. Brevity of tweets provides opportunities for text mining and trend analysis across traffic streams. Use of tags enhances this.
Yammer®	A microblogging service similar to Twitter®, focused on organizations – each organization's network is private, and is based on email domain. Groups within the company can be formed. Basic membership is free, with paid advanced services and configurations available. Tweets are short, but not limited to 140 characters, and may have attachments.	
Social Bookmarking	Bookmarks are saved on a website with user-assigned tags, and thus may be identified/accessed in multiple contexts. Bookmarks are available to other users (general public or established "friends") or may be kept private.	User's bookmarks are available on any networked computer using any browser. Users with common interests benefit from each other's bookmarks, simply by searching on tags.
Portals	An extension to traditional dynamic Web applications; combines fragments provided by portlets (various applications and/or servers) into a single Web page. Portals and Web 2.0 services can cross-reference each other. Portal technology is mature and widely used throughout NASA.	Promotes seamlessness from a user perspective.

Term	Explanation	Comments
Webinar	Web-based seminar. . . A workshop or lecture delivered over the Web. . . may be a one-way Webcast, or there may be interaction between the audience and the presenters. May include audio and/or video streams.	In addition to enabling remote presentation of charts, many webinar applications include text chat, multivoting, and other interactive features that, when recorded, capture the collaborative process.
Enterprise Social Software	Combinations of social software and networked modifications to corporate intranets and other classic software platforms. Used by large companies to organize their communication	A major component of Enterprise 2.0 ("a system of web-based technologies that provide rapid and agile collaboration, information sharing, emergence and integration capabilities in the extended enterprise") It is worth noting that while traditional enterprise software imposes content structure on users, enterprise social software allows users to define the structure of the content

Table 1 – Some Major Web 2.0-Related Techniques and Applications [3]

WHY ARE SOCIAL MEDIA IMPORTANT?

There are distinct differences between data, information, and knowledge:

- Data is fact without context.
- Information is data presented in context.
- Knowledge of what to do with information enables sound decision making, regardless of project phase.

The bottom line is that PEOPLE hold the knowledge, even if assisted by databases, web sites, and the like. Social media and networking link people more effectively, resulting in better knowledge sharing and better decisions. [4] It does this in at least two ways:

- Collaborative tools enable conversations among known interested parties across geographic and/or time gaps, and by capturing and/or cataloguing the results instantly.
- Search engines introduce conversations to previously unknown interested parties, multiplying collective knowledge and participation.

There is so much more to operations and engineering than just the results or deliverables. Process and interim results can be as important as (and sometimes more important than) final products, especially for follow-on and/or derivative projects and efforts. Social media and other modern tools enable real-time capture of both the relationships and transactions that comprise the knowledge sharing process, concurrently with simplifying work that needs doing anyway. This leads to insights and opportunities that are otherwise missed.

The author believes that adoption of social media as an everyday working tool has been slow for three main reasons:

- The best-known examples, e.g., Facebook® and Twitter®, have been experienced, and often merely observed as activities of our friends and/or families, in the sense of “social” as “friendly companionship or relations.”
- We have so much work to do that we don’t think we can afford the time and risk needed to learn new, potentially more effective methods.
- Social media have a very open structure and rely heavily on dynamic group authorship. This feels awkward and risky compared to the traditional “review and approve” or “let’s get all our ducks in a row before sharing” approach.

If we reframe “social” as referring to the interactions among organisms and their collective co-existence, perhaps we’ll give as much attention to our means of communication as we give to the interactions among aeronautical systems and their collective co-existence.

USING SOCIAL MEDIA FOR ENGINEERING SUPPORT

A. Blogs, wikis, RSSs

For engineering support, blogs and wikis support group dialog and/or authorship free of the redundancies, confusion, and clutter of email chains, as shown in Figures 3 and 4.

Email Communication Thread

Participants update addresses and forward/reply manually.
 Message fragments easily added/deleted.
 Entire messages easily deleted, lost, or mis-filed.
 Inbox cluttered with multiple messages on same topic.

Blog Communication Thread

Can configure blog engine to:
 Invite new participants
 Identify contributing participant, date, time
 Hide ID info to promote honest brainstorming
 Notify participants of changes by email, text msg, Twitter
 Participants can opt-in or opt-out of notifications.
 Deleting or omitting notifications doesn't lose access to content.
 Content stays in foreground, never lost among headers/fragments.

Figure 3 – Blog vs. Email [5]

Email Collaboration

Wiki Collaboration

Figure 4 – Wiki vs. Email [5]

The distinction between blogs and wikis is that the former shows each contributor's individual inputs in some sort of sequence, e.g., by time and/or by thread, while a wiki shows a convergent sculpture resulting from the group's inputs. Archiving of a wiki's previous versions, including identification of editors, is automatic with each save. Most wikis provide A vs. B comparison and often have a separate tab for discussion comments. Such discussions are often very blog-like. Generally speaking, blogs instigate and capture conversations while wikis create a product.

Wikis may appear to involve lack of control ("anyone can edit"), which is no doubt disconcerting to those accustomed to rigorous document configuration management, e.g., engineers! A social media purist would answer that what really happens in a wiki is that ownership is vested in the group rather than an individual purporting to represent the group, and that convergence occurs far more quickly than traditional methods. Wikipedia is more comprehensive and up-to-date than even online versions of classic encyclopedias. Why? Because the vast majority of readers really do care about truth, entries that are "off" by any significant amount get corrected. Many technical documents do need to have tight locks and to be better than "good enough", but the author believes that much formative work and/or major revision could be done more effectively via wikis, and that some non-critical reference works could be written entirely that way, especially since traceability is built in.

An in-between approach would be to establish a convention that authors provide their comments and suggested edits in the desired locations within the wiki, but do so by adding material in brackets and/or in different colors. Comments by multiple authors recommending the same type of change would show consensus. The official editor could either revise the wiki to his/her best interpretation of the suggestions and request additional review, or decisions could be made and implemented in a group meeting.

Discoverability of social media is a significant added benefit compared to traditional methods – search engines, user and author-assigned tags, and inclusion in RSS feeds allow interested parties not on distribution lists to find relevant items and join the conversation if access permissions allow. All this, and, again, automatic archiving. Here are some concrete suggestions related to engineering support, based on the author's experience:

- Orientation and training. While the author was developing Ares I Upper Stage training in 2007-2008, one of the most frequent concerns voiced by engineers and managers was not having a big picture of what other teams were working on and "worrying" about. A major part of this problem stemmed from a) having an ocean of information too big to sort through, especially when standing outside a particular discipline, and b) formal documentation takes too long to catch up with current reality. The "highly accessible and scalable

publishing capability" of social media can overcome these challenges brilliantly.

- In any environment, wikis work well for encyclopedia functions – defining terms, explaining "how-to's", "gotchas", and the like. Uncontrolled wikis could be used to capture guidance, advice, and issues for escalation to other forums. A more controlled, wiki-based glossary could show established terms, identify proposed and approved additions or changes. Official revision can be decreed more frequently with little or no cost.

- Discuss major concepts, themes, and issues during each phase of document preparation, embedding links to specific documents or, better yet, to appropriate locations within those documents. This would be especially useful in flagging and tracking cross-disciplinary items. More detailed discussions could be linked to the major ones, and vice versa.

- Support formal document reviews. At the very least, this could lubricate the interchange between Review Item Discrepancy (RID) authors and RID reviewers, and among reviewers prior to contacting authors. Ideally, RID management could move away from manual handling of "Change wording from" and "Change wording to" spreadsheets to a wiki-based system with capabilities to spawn side discussions and keep track of dependencies within or across documents. Hyperlinks and/or floating windows might let participants see proposed changes in context. It should also be possible to submit graphics integrally in a RID. The author knows of a developer who is working on precisely such an application, and there are probably others.

- Rigorous configuration management (CM) is an obvious need for engineering efforts, especially for space and human-rated systems, yet wikis produce more rapid convergence on "truth" than traditional methods of document circulation and review. Standard wiki editing adopts all changes and saves archive copies, but tracing all changes via version comparison could be awkward. Perhaps a wiki/blog mashup might be able to control a linked discussion with moderation by the document manager. This could improve both the quality and speed of modifications by orders of magnitude.

- RSS provides an ideal mechanism for making information available to all who have an interest, without bludgeoning their email inboxes. There are ample provisions for access restriction, if needed. Mandatory reviewers can be notified via traditional email distribution lists.

B. Social Network Services.

A major inhibitor to using SNSs at work is apprehension about being open with one's profile. This is quite understandable, given the free-for-all appearance of extremely popular sites like Facebook® and Twitter® and the images of frivolity they conjure up. Using more closed environments such as Yammer, or an SNS embedded in a major engineering site should provide intimacy to encourage participation. Facebook®-like SNSs have great potential for promoting and capturing the "hall talk" that keeps us connected as people, bolsters our capacity for technical discussion, and often produces the back-of-the-napkin sketch that leads to major solutions.

C. Microblogging

It's generally known that the original basis of Twitter® was "In 140 characters or less, answer the question, 'What are you doing now?'" If that's all one does with the service, it stands to reason that traffic can easily become boring, especially if it's just people describing their daily doings.

Of course, there have been some good twists on this. For example, progress on some Martian rover missions has been broadcast as though the rover was a "person." In addition to having public appeal, the tweets provided an excellent "big picture" of what was going on. This same method could be valuable for real time engineering support of launch and/or rocket stage and engine test operations. Tweets could be generated manually and/or automatically, depending on what information is intended. As usual, followers can tailor reception preferences to match their needs for instant vs. when-convenient review of information.

The above is still a "What are you doing now?" approach. More value can be added by tweeting "above the noise" moments (e.g., "Aha!", "Oh, nuts!", "Hmmm, that's weird...") or appeals for help on questions/issues. These can be followed up with more detailed discussion via other social media, email, phone, or face-to-face meetings. The power of the technique is automatic notification of those who are following the tweeter who, in a workplace setting, have a common interest. This is especially true for microblogging schemes implemented in a restricted domain that already represents the interest, e.g., Yammer®.

One might say that microblogging services let us create stock tickers for any subject

D. Partition and Conquer

Email messages intrinsically clamor for one's attention, and one feels obligated to do something with them. Social media content can be kept isolated from your email, reducing the pressure in the fire hose you've been drinking from. By using tags and by being selective in which threads and people you "follow", when you do take the time and to go fishing in the social media pond, you'll find yourself in

relevance-infested waters! (The ideas swimming with you are dolphins, not sharks.)

ENHANCING FLIGHT CONTROL OPERATIONS USING SOCIAL MEDIA

This discussion includes suggestions for both **nominal applications** of Social Media (that would benefit both common office settings and operations environments) and **ops-unique applications**. Most of these ideas, especially for ops-unique applications, are embryonic, and would require some modification of existing social media engines. One purpose of this paper is to encourage (and provoke!) lively discussion that morphs into deeper analysis, followed by practical evolution. One way to get real is to dream first.

A. Blogs

Concept: Use blogs to replace email threads concerning specific issues [nominal application].

These applications would be essentially the same as discussed for Engineering Support.

Concept: Use blogs as position-specific console logs [ops-unique application].

At MSFC's Payload Operations Integration Center (POIC), each console position maintains a console log, which is defined as "a brief narrative of significant operational events". This definition goes back decades to the Spacelab Program of the 1980s and 1990s, and the concept of operations logs literally goes back to ancient times. Today's technology makes it possible to capture an incredible amount of data. Operations personnel have a natural tendency to strive for comprehensiveness, so the challenge now is robust capture yet simple presentation.

An enhanced blog engine for console logging might have the following characteristics:

- Automatic entry of full date-time group, operator name (may have more than one operator working a position concurrently), and field for entering "source" of entry (e.g., voice loop, email, telemetry, etc.)
- Log entries would be very short synopses of results or issues, but could have "magic links" to underlying details. Such a link would be created by merely highlighting the desired portion of detailed source material (which of course may live in any of a number of mission systems) and dragging into the blog. By default, the detailed material content would be hidden, but could be viewed within the log entry or opened in a separate window, and just as easily re-hidden. The detailed material itself would not actually be pasted into the blog.
- Able to handle graphics, video, and other media. In some situations, it may be better to link than to paste or embed.

- Pasting of messages from monitoring systems, e.g., Caution & Warning. (Could be automatic, or could notify operator of condition and ask if log entry desired. There could be interesting variations for supporting reduced staffing.)
- Support for speech-to-text conversion of voice loop audio when literal transcripts are desired.
- Support for treating and/or displaying some threads as side-bar items, e.g., summarized in the blog, visible as needed, then hidden to avoid clutter.
- Viewable in real-time by appropriate parties other than the console operator (e.g., off-console personnel from the same team, other real-time and/or back room positions, and supervisors) so they can be cognizant of what is in work.
- Able to accept comments from appropriate external parties. Authority and responsibility for a position's activities always lies with the on-duty operator. However, a teammate who happened to be viewing the blog might have knowledge or insight that could benefit the real-time effort and/or be useful from a post-operations perspective. It is important to be able to capture such "in the moment" thoughts in the context that inspired them. One could have a very interesting discussion about when these comments should be visible and invisible, and to whom. Any provision for external comments must clearly identify them as such.
- Allow the console operator to easily send entries and/or notifications messages to individuals and/or distribution lists. The sender provides message content, message

priority (e.g., routine, priority, urgent), and destination(s); a messaging engine would route messages according to recipient-provided preferences for each priority.

- Multi-tiered administrative privileges:
 - Select members of a given team control read/write privileges for their team's blog
 - Select members of the overseeing project control which privileges the "team admins" can assign
 - A facility administrator and/or sysop controls what the "project admin" can do.
 - Higher level admins can fill in for lower level admins when needed.
 - This would let teams fine-tune their blogs to meet unique needs, subject to project oversight, and would relieve facility staff of undue burden. (The inmates often know the best way to run the institution.)

The notions of external viewing and/or comment capability introduced in the paragraph above could involve quite a stretch of operations philosophy. While console logs must fulfill their initial purpose, there could be tremendous value from a systems and/or lifecycle perspective in enabling logs to feed and/or receive information to/from other contexts. There is so much linkage in the things we do. We might as well take advantage of technology's burgeoning ability to capture it and navigate it so that we can gain deeper insight and make better real-time and off-line decisions.

Concept: Establish a central blog for a given control facility [ops-unique application]. See Figure 5.

Figure 5 – "Central Blog" for an Operations Control Facility

In many flight control rooms, there is a main voice loop, typically named after the lead flight controller position in the facility, that carries voice traffic about the operation's "big picture" issues and decisions. Generally speaking, all controllers in that facility are required to monitor the main loop and it is not unusual for some external facilities listen in as well. For ISS, the FLIGHT (Flight Director) loop at Mission Control Center Houston (MCC-H) is monitored by all ISS control facilities around the world. Use of a Central Blog, similarly visible to "all", could provide a page for "all" to use. Read and write privileges would be controlled similarly to talk and listen privileges for voice loops.

Characteristics of a Central Blog might be similar to those discussed in the position-specific blog concept, particularly those of a blog that allows main inputs or entries (as opposed to comments on entries) from concurrent console operators on the same team.

The right-hand side of Figure 4 depicts Integrated and Split views of the Central Blog with respect to position-specific logs/blogs. Users should be able to switch back and forth between these views as best suits their need at a given time. The author believes that the Integrated View would be most useful to those working real-time issues, as position-specific log entries could be seen in the context of Central Blog activity. Careful design of the interface would permit operators to work seamlessly on their position-specific or Central Blog entries and threads. The Split View seems to make sense for support work, e.g., the operator is not in the thick of here-and-now decisions, but needs cognizance of operational flow.

Concept: Establish a multi-author blog for a console operations team working subordinate to the control facility level. [ops-unique application].

This would be essentially a hybrid of the position-specific and Central Blog concepts described above. The Team Blog would allow for entry creation by multiple console positions within the team and comments to entries by authorized external parties. Various combinations of Integrated and Split views would be possible, and would be controlled by team administrators rather than facility system operators.

B. Wikis

Concept: Use wikis for maintaining uncontrolled and/or semi-formal documents that are internal to a team [nominal application]

These uses are very similar to those for Engineering Support. An operations environment example would be a console operations handbook. A defining characteristic might be that while organized cognizance is needed, such documents do not need full-up configuration management.

Concept: Use wikis for periodic documents such as daily status reports and shift tag-ups [ops-unique application].

Preparation of regular status reports often involves sending reports to a central position or person for integration into a finished product, which means someone ends up cutting and pasting (and perhaps losing a few tidbits). Group authorship eliminates the wasted motion. It might even be possible for certain information to be posted or updated automatically by a monitoring system.

It is not unusual for a shift to tag-up on the voice loops soon after handover. The trouble is that some team members may be working contingencies or otherwise be unavailable during the tag-up, so each position writes their own notes based on whatever they hear or do not hear. If voice loop archive playback is available, a position could review the tag-up, but this requires more time and would distract from here-and-now duties. If the team prepared a wiki in advance of the tag-up, everyone could get a basic sense of current activity and significant issues at a glance. The wiki could then be refined based on comments made during the live conversation.

C. Social Network Sites/Services and Microblogging

Nominal applications would be essentially the same as discussed for Engineering Support.

Concept: Use microblogging to maintain a running operations "hall conversation" [ops-unique application]

Example: At POIC, control center positions have email addresses with a much narrower email domain than "@nasa.gov" and authorized flight controllers can be uniquely identified by their work email addresses. Yammer activity within such a small population could be extremely fruitful. Why? This sort of group consists of approximately 300 flight controllers and facility support personnel filling about 25 functional positions with inter-related goals and concerns. The people also know each other reasonably well as friends. Yammer posts would probably appear in small clumps (initial post and a few replies, then other replies and/or threads beginning some time later), providing the intimacy of 2 to 5 people speaking casually, but the ideas would be accessible to all, across time (different shifts and duty days) and distance (travel to meetings at other centers). It would be good to let users identify yams (the Yammer version of tweets) by their position, name, both, or neither: both identity and anonymity have value.

Variation: Embed microblog capability in a console log tool so that the essentials of what's "popping up above the noise" can be captured and transmitted "while the iron is hot." Eligible followers would be limited to those with log access. Automated and/or human analysis of entries issued across the project could be an extremely powerful tool.

SOME CURRENT USES IN NASA ENGINEERING SUPPORT AND FLIGHT CONTROL OPERATIONS

The author is aware of four large-scale engineering support efforts that include social media capabilities:

- The former Constellation Program's Integrated Collaborative Environment (ICE) has several thousand registered users and may be expanded to serve a variety of Exploration and other projects across the Agency. It has wiki capabilities that are customized to user organization preferences and also supports traditional applications for file management, requirements definition, etc. Blogging and other Web 2.0 applications could be added.
- The NASA Engineering Network, sponsored by the NASA Office of the Chief Engineer, serves several thousand NASA engineers across the agency with technical communities of practice for disciplines such as Guidance Navigation and Control, Structures, and Systems Engineering. The service includes a semantic search engine, wikis, forums, expertise location, collaborative document authoring, and sharing of NASA lessons learned.
- MSFC's Engineering Knowledge Management (ME KM) system, which went "live" in early 2010 after 4 years of development, embeds engineering practice and workflows to capture and reuse knowledge, best practices, and lessons learned. It provides access to internal/external information, knowledge content, training and subject matter expertise, and is offered as a Center-wide professional collaboration and enterprise search platform.
- MSFC's Advanced Engineering Operations Network (AEON), is a web-based portal, originally created for Ares I for accessing and analyzing Ares manufacturing, test, and performance data, and for establishing user communities, including blog and wiki capabilities.

The following flight operations applications have come to the author's attention:

- A satellite operations team at UC Berkeley has configured its exception monitoring equipment to automatically Twitter® team members if certain conditions arise until a team member notifies the computer that the message has been received. That team member then assumes responsibility for coming in or logging in to the control center to address the problem.
- At JSC's Mission Control Center Houston (MCC-H), some non-critical communications between front and back rooms are handled via instant messaging (IM), reducing some voice loop and email clutter. (However, MCC-H does not treat IM as official information.) Also, a wiki-driven reference-only knowledge base of tips, tricks, and lessons learned is maintained, indexed by discipline and discipline-specific subcategories, with "search across all" capability.

- MSFC's Huntsville Operations Support Center (HOSC) is expanding AEON to include a portal for providing "one stop shop" services to the International Space Station (ISS) payload operations community and other projects, and is currently prototyping a console log tool embodying some of the concepts described in this paper. While originally intended for ISS payload operations, the tool may become available in generic form for adaptation to a wide variety of missions and/or projects. One feature worth noting is having administrators from the user organization, as opposed to System Administrators, perform most of the project-unique and position-unique configuration, privilege assignment, and data field definition. This is consistent with the Web 2.0 concept of users controlling content and presentation.

The author welcomes news of other engineering and/or operations uses of social media.

ANCILLARY TOPICS

While the main thrust of this paper is the use of social media for engineering support and space flight control operations, the author's discussions and correspondence with others (and his own musings) have uncovered some related themes that merit a few words.

A. Collaborative Software, Tools, Groupware, etc.

Social media are star clusters within a galaxy of tools available for facilitating group efforts. A brief overview on this broader topic, including discussion of some design considerations, is at (short link <http://bit.ly/huHXgq>). A "small" categorized glimpse of specific applications may be seen at (short link <http://bit.ly/br4koA>).

This paper has mentioned mashups as a way to create new collaborative capabilities. One example that the author recently discovered combines an online word processor with a commenting and revision tracking system⁴.

B. Decision Support Systems (DSSs)

This type of collaboration tool is well-suited for facilitating meetings and for implementing techniques associated with group decision-making methods such as Kaizen Analysis, Quality Circles, Continuous Improvement, Total Quality Management (TQM), etc. DSSs typically allow simultaneous, anonymous inputs and/or comments on a given topic and support multiple types of voting schemes, with results posted instantly. Simultaneous input results in massively parallel inputs and often triggers development and expression of innovative ideas that would otherwise remain dormant. Anonymity reduces positional and/or personal stresses among participants.

⁴ See <http://www.redliner.com/>

DSS collaboration sessions may be held synchronously or asynchronously in single or distributed locations. Voting results show areas of consensus and nonconsensus, often with inclusion of statistics such as standard deviation. (Even if there's consensus on a given item, a large deviation points to areas that may merit more discussion.) In synchronous meetings, DSS-aided groups can often accomplish more in 2 to 6 hours (in terms of generating/evaluating/prioritizing ideas, building preliminary action plans, and having everything *documented*) than they could in several days .⁵

C. Videoconferencing and Web Conferencing

Videoconferencing and webinars are not “highly scalable”, but they definitely have social aspects to them and can contribute significantly to collaboration.

Desktop videoconferencing has been readily available for 15 years or so, as has screen sharing (passing screen draw and keyboard/mouse commands across the network, with remote workstations performing the graphics work to recreate the screen image being observed and/or controlled). Most solutions involved dedicated software on the desktop and direct communications with participating nodes, or sometimes a server. Until fairly recently, neither function had caught on in a big way.

Early videoconferencing products either involved inordinately high expense or rather low quality. Today's technology can transmit excellent quality video at low bandwidths (e.g., 720p, the resolution of first-generation HDTV, at 1 Mb/sec).

The challenge with video is more cultural than technical. A few years ago, a group that videoconferenced weekly went back to teleconferencing because offline remarks, while not audible, were visible, and the body language created negative impressions, leaving the viewer to imagine the words! In this case, the stress relief (in both directions) of being able to make private offline comments was more important than having constant visual contact.

⁵MSFC currently uses Group Systems' ThinkTank® application. This is not so say that video should be avoided per se. Occasional videoconferences can positively reinforce the personal relationships that make for good exchanges via phone, email, and social media. And of course, if there are products or methods to demonstrate, video is the next best thing to being there.

Web conferencing tools are predominantly web-based and are seeing wider usage, particularly environments such as Webex® and Elluminate®, which often include text chat and multiple polling or other feedback tools in addition to the primary document display. Much of the innovation in conferencing is taking place in the e-training industry. From a habit and cultural standpoint, it's important for folks to learn how to present, teach, and/or moderate in an e-sharing

environment; traditional conference room or auditorium approaches do not work very well in such settings.

D. Cloud Computing

The author has been asked how cloud computing relates to social media. They are not tightly intertwined, though social media applications are often hosted “in the cloud.” Cloud computing provides distributed, rapidly scalable processing capability over the internet, typically on a utility (pay-for-capacity-used) or subscription (access for X period of time) basis. This frees the paying entity from the burden of maintaining the physical and software infrastructure needed to run the application. The cloud metaphor arises because processing (and related data) is not in specified, known or static places, There are several deployment methods – public, community, private, hybrid, etc. More restricted deployments provide ways to address security and reliability concerns that naturally arise for mission critical operations. NASA is developing a hybrid cloud capability (nebula.nasa.gov).

Wikipedia's “cloud computing” entry provides a jumping off point for more information.

E. Institutional Use of Social Media at NASA

This is a very broad topic indeed, and will not be discussed in depth here. This is a synopsis of the author's perception of current efforts, based on relatively casual observation:

- Sophisticated social media capabilities have been implemented for public outreach. Doug Guthrie of New York University School of Business ranked NASA as having the highest “Digital IQ Index” of U.S. public sector organizations. [6]
- In August 2010, an Agency-wide policy titled “Social Networking Tools and Web 2.0 - Appropriate Use of Web Technologies” was established. [7]
- An agency-wide wiki site has been established and is available to all NASA civil service and contractor personnel with a valid Agency User ID (AUID) – inwiki.nasa.gov.
- An enterprise social software architecture (including integration with traditional office tools) has not been established. Individual centers are experimenting with various social media approaches. MSFC plans to “go live” with an internal Social Networking Service named ExplorNet in February 2010.

F. Special Note - A Humble Yet Mighty Servant: Tags

(A transition back to the social media discussion)

Spider silk has a tensile strength comparable to that of high grade steel. Tags are discoverability's spider silk, and discoverability – the ease of finding new (from the reader's perspective), relevant material - is a key benefit of using social media. The benefit is proportional to participation by both readers and writers in assigning tags.

OVERCOMING BARRIERS TO CONCEPT CONSIDERATION AND IMPLEMENTATION

The biggest obstacle to reaping the potential benefits of these tools and techniques crops up in most corporate cultures and across most topics. People and organizations often avoid investing the time and risk of learning methods that differ from the status quo because “There’s too much work that needs doing right now.” This phenomenon might be reduced if organizations budgeted work time for their members to spend some effort exploring and “playing” with alternative techniques outside of day-to-day activity. Professional athletes are given time to stretch and condition; engineers and console operators deserve no less.

In addition to individual efforts, exercises that involve trying things we might never do in real life could germinate desirable changes. For example, run a 2-hour simulation in which all transactions normally made by voice communication are handled via text chat or blog, then contemplate what types of messages could be more effectively handled in a similar manner. This could reduce both the amount of voice traffic required and the number of “say again” requests.

While exploration of new techniques can be somewhat free-wheeling, actual changes to the control room regime should be made with deliberation. A lot of resources and even human life may be at stake. While current processes may have room for significant improvement, they do work. In operations, better or best can be the enemy of “good enough”. The problem is that as data and demands increase, current methods may fall below the line of being good enough.

One way to emerge gently into the use of social media is to use a new method and/or tool for a minor, lighthearted, or even whimsical task, e.g., coordinating office participation in the company’s charity fundraising drive, planning a party, designing a rocket with components you could find on a desert isle, etc. (Stretching prior to vigorous exercise prevents injuries, enhances performance, and increases endurance.)

In some cases, transition to new methods and tools can be eased from the development side by making the new process or tool interface look similar to the old one, then gradually morphing the interface for improved effectiveness or functionality.

CONCLUSION

Social media is gradually working its way into the fabric of NASA office life. NASA field centers and engineering projects are experimenting with social software suites.

This paper has not addressed social media security issues in any depth, but these should be manageable.

The major challenge to adoption of social media collaboration methods in engineering support and flight operations control is the same as that facing organizations in general: spawning cultural change by education and training to overcome stereotyped views and attitudes and to encourage the transition from “push” to “many-to-many” Fundamentals may be taught with modest resources. One place to dip one’s feet into the water is an MSFC-sponsored primer at <http://engagedlearning.net/post/social-media-challenge-final-post> (short link <http://bit.ly/8rPon6>).

Social media can dramatically improve a) the density and organization of relevant information exchange among engineering support and/or personnel and b) the efficiency, capture, and tagging of collaborative activity as it occurs. At the same time, extreme care must be taken in defining permissions and wielding the awesome power of discoverability, for once information is out there, it’s really hard to get it back!

Blogs and wikis can be used generically to strip away the overhead and confusion of email chains, keeping focus on the content. Generally speaking, blogs capture conversations and wikis generate products. Wikis are auto-archived, group-authored web pages, and there is typically a blog-like Discussion area associated with each wiki page, plus arrangements for nesting and hyperlinking pages.

Applying social media techniques to specialized operations applications such as console operator logs can integrate fundamental purposes (e.g., a brief narrative of significant operational events) with social processes that drive decisionmaking and capture insight.

Microblogging has tremendous potential for capturing events and thoughts above and below general noise levels. These in turn can reveal trends that lead to sound decisionmaking on how best to improve processes and tools.

As with any technology, two activities at the beginning and end of the selection process are essential. Play with the technology and methods at multiple levels of the organization, initially with projects of little or no strategic importance. (This makes it safe to learn the possibilities.) Implement social media tools and methods because they produce gain, not for the sake of adoption.

Experiment broadly, then be choosy about what to implement for “production.” Repeat often – continuously, if possible.

SPRINGBOARDS FOR FURTHER INSIGHT

The author has established a space for social exploration and refinement of the topics covered in this paper at <http://www.govloop.com/group/smesops>. It is not necessary to be a government employee to sign up. A starting place for finding bookmarks of direct and indirect interest may be found at http://www.delicious.com/scotty_at_msfc. Be sure to surf elsewhere within “delicious”, and work those tags!

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BIOGRAPHY

David W. Scott, alias “Scotty”, is currently developing innovative interfaces and applications for the Huntsville Operations Support Center (HOSC) at NASA’s Marshall Space Flight Center in support of ISS payload operations. He was a Payload Communications Manager for the International Space Station from 1999-2007. He

has spearheaded several console technology projects, especially in space-to-ground videoconferencing and audio archiving. He was a payload communicator for the ATLAS-1 Spacelab mission in 1992, and helped design the payload training program for Space Station. He spent 6 years as a U.S. Naval Officer, including flight duty in F-14s, and holds a B.S. in Physics and Mathematics from Principia College.